

AN INFORMATION THEORETIC APPROACH TO BLIND MULTIPLE ACCESS INTERFERENCE SUPPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the problem of blind interference cancellation in Direct Sequence Code Division Multiple Access (DS CDMA) systems. The Maximum Likelihood (ML) criterion is used to estimate the coefficients of a linear filter that suppresses both Multiple Access Interference (MAI) and Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI). Block-iterative and adaptive algorithms based on the Space Alternating Generalized Expectation-Maximization (SAGE) approach are proposed and their performance is compared with existing Linearly Constrained Minimum Variance (LCMV) blind receivers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) has been chosen as the basic multiple access scheme of third generation wideband mobile communication systems because of its spectral efficiency and flexibility in the radio interface [1]. However, practical CDMA systems are limited by the Multiple Access Interference (MAI) due to the different users transmitting simultaneously in the same frequency band and the Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) caused by the time dispersive effects of the radio channel.

Different techniques have been proposed to suppress both MAI and ISI using linear filtering. Decorrelating receivers require a perfect knowledge of the user codes whereas Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) approaches suffer from the need of training sequences [2]. Therefore, alternative blind implementations have been preferred [2, 3, 4]. Most blind schemes, however, are based on the Linearly Constrained Minimum Variance (LCMV) criterion that requires a very precise knowledge of the desired user spreading code and timing [2]. Constant Modulus (CM) receivers are more robust but do not improve the convergence speed [3]. Subspace techniques with somehow faster convergence rate have also been suggested but they are limited by their high computational complexity [4].

In this paper we propose a new blind approach to interference cancellation that exploits the available statistical information of the signal of interest and takes into account the Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) in the channel. The Space Alternating Generalized

Expectation-Maximization (SAGE) method is employed to compute the Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimate of the linear receiver that suppresses both MAI and ISI. A linear constraint is set in order to ensure the extraction of the desired user. Additionally, a computationally efficient adaptive implementation of the SAGE algorithm is investigated.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the signal model. In section 3 we introduce the ML linear blind multiuser receiver. Sections 4 and 5 present the iterative and adaptive implementations, respectively. Section 6 shows some computer simulations results and, finally, section 7 is devoted to the conclusions.

2 SIGNAL MODEL

Figure 1: Asynchronous DS CDMA system.

Let us consider the asynchronous baseband discrete-time equivalent model of a Direct Sequence (DS) CDMA system with time dispersive channels shown in figure 1. Each user i is assigned a unique code sequence $c_i(k)$, $k = 0, \dots, L - 1$ and the resulting signal is passed through a linear time-dispersive channel, $h_i(k)$, $k = 0, \dots, P - 1$ that accounts for the continuous-time channel response, the relative time delays of the different users and the transmitter and receiver front-end filters. The resulting received signal is given by the equation,

$$x(k) = \sum_{i=1}^N d_i(k)b_i + g(k), \quad k = 0, \dots, L + P - 2 \quad (1)$$

where $d_i(k) = c_i(k) * h_i(k) = \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} h_i(p)c_i(k - p)$ is the *distorted received code*. Since the symbol $b_i(n)$ interferes with $b_i(n - 1), \dots, b_i(n - m + 1)$, where $m = \lceil \frac{L+P-1}{L} \rceil$ is

the channel memory size, the overall received sequence during the n -th symbol period is

$$x(n, k) = x(nL + k) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} d_i(r, k) b_i(n-r) + g(k),$$

$$k = 0, \dots, L-1 \quad (2)$$

where $d_i(r, k) = d_i(rL + k)$. Using vector notation, the observations in (2) can be written as

$$\mathbf{x}(n) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{b}_i(n) + \mathbf{g}(n) \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(n) = [x(0), \dots, x(L-1)]^T$ is the $L \times 1$ observation vector, $\mathbf{D}_i = [\mathbf{d}_i(0), \dots, \mathbf{d}_i(m-1)]$ is the $L \times m$ received code matrix for the i -th user, composed of the column vectors $\mathbf{d}_i(r) = [d_i(r, 0), \dots, d_i(r, L-1)]^T$; $\mathbf{b}_i(n) = [b_i(n), \dots, b_i(n-m+1)]^T$ is the $m \times 1$ vector of symbols contributed by the i -th user to the n -th observation vector and $\mathbf{g}(n) = [g_1(n), \dots, g_L(n)]^T$ is a vector of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) complex Gaussian variables with zero mean and variance σ_g^2 .

The considered linear multiuser receiver (see figure 1) consists of a FIR filter, $\mathbf{w} = [w_1, \dots, w_L]^T$, followed by a threshold detector. The soft estimate corresponding to the n -th symbol period can be written as

$$y(n) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{x}(n), \quad (4)$$

where the superindex H denotes Hermitian transposition.

3 SELECTION OF THE FILTER COEFFICIENTS

Let us denote $\mathbf{w}_*$ as the optimum value of the filter coefficients that totally eliminates both the MAI and the ISI. Then, the soft symbol estimate, y , consists of just two components: the desired user symbol, b_1 , and an additive Gaussian noise term, g_f , with zero mean and variance $\sigma_f^2 = \sigma_g^2 \mathbf{w}_*^H \mathbf{w}_*$, i.e.,

$$y = \mathbf{w}_*^H \mathbf{x} = A_1 b_1 + g_f. \quad (5)$$

In the sequel, we will assume, for simplicity, that the noise variance σ_f^2 is constant. Simulations will show that this assumption does not lead to a performance degradation.

Considering that blocks of K observation vectors are received and taking into account that the transmitted symbols are modelled as discrete i.i.d. random variables with known probability density function (p.d.f.) and finite alphabet, we can derive the joint p.d.f. of a data frame, $\mathbf{y} = [y(0), \dots, y(K-1)]^T$, as [5]

$$f_{\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{w}_*, A_1}(\mathbf{y}) = \left(\frac{1}{\pi \sigma_f^2} \right)^K \prod_{n=0}^{K-1} E_b \left[e^{-\frac{|y(n) - A_1 b|^2}{\sigma_f^2}} \right] \quad (6)$$

where $E_b[\cdot]$ denotes statistical expectation with respect to (w.r.t.) the desired user symbol and can be analytically

calculated. The p.d.f. of $\mathbf{y}$ in (6) depends on the unknown parameters $\mathbf{w}_*$ and A_1 . Therefore, the ML estimates of $\mathbf{w}_*$ and A_1 turn out to be

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{\mathbf{w}}, \hat{A}_1] &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{w}_*, A_1} \{ \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}_*, A_1) = \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} \log E_b \left[e^{-\frac{|y(n) - A_1 b|^2}{\sigma_f^2}} \right] \} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}_*, A_1)$ is the log-likelihood of $[\mathbf{w}_*, A_1]$ w.r.t. the observed data $\mathbf{y} = [y(0), \dots, y(K-1)]$.

The log-likelihood $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}_*, A_1)$ is a non quadratic function with several maxima. In particular, the solutions to problem (7) guarantee that the soft estimates, $y(n)$, have a p.d.f. close to $f_{A_1 b + g_f}(\cdot)$. Since all users in CDMA transmit symbols with the same modulation format, the p.d.f. of the i -th interference at the receiver is $f_{A_i b + g_f}(\cdot)$ which only differs from the target p.d.f., $f_{A_1 b + g_f}(\cdot)$, in the unknown complex amplitude $A_1 \neq A_i$. Thus, the receiver may be *captured* by an interference user instead of the desired one. In order to avoid this problem we propose to set a linear constraint on the coefficient vector $\mathbf{w}$ that prevents the extraction of a non desired user [5]. Let us consider the following factorization of $\mathbf{d}_i(r)$,

$$\mathbf{d}_i(r) = \mathbf{C}_i(r) \mathbf{h}_i \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_i = [h_i(0), \dots, h_i(P-1)]^T$ is the $P \times 1$ vector containing the channel components for the i -th user and

$$\mathbf{C}_i(r) = \begin{bmatrix} c_i(rL) & \dots & c_i(rL-P) \\ \dots & \ddots & \dots \\ c_i(rL+L-1) & \dots & c_i(rL+L-1-P) \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

is a $L \times P$ matrix obtained from the i -th user transmitted code. Using this decomposition, the soft estimate $y(n)$ can be written as

$$y(n) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{C}_1(0) \mathbf{h}_1 b_1(n) + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{d}_1(i) b_1(n-i) + \sum_{i=2}^N \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{b}_i + \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{g}(n) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{d}_1(0) b_1(n)$ is the desired signal component and the other terms correspond to the ISI, MAI and noise respectively. The filter vector, $\mathbf{w}$, is constrained to verify

$$\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{C}_1(0) \mathbf{h}_1 = A_1 \quad (11)$$

as long as $\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{C}_1(0) = \mathbf{u}^T = [0 \dots 0 \underbrace{1}_d 0 \dots 0]$ and

$|h_1(d)| > 0$. The linearly constrained ML estimation problem can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{\mathbf{w}}, \hat{A}_1] &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{w}_*, A_1} \{ \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}_*, A_1) = \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} \log E_b \left[e^{-\frac{|y(n) - A_1 b|^2}{\sigma_f^2}} \right] \} \\ &\text{subject to } \mathbf{w}_*^H \mathbf{C}_1(0) = \mathbf{u}^T. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

It is important to remark that, rigorously speaking, criterion (12) is inherently unrealizable because it relies on the hypothesis that the soft estimates $y(n)$ have the *desired* p.d.f. It is apparent that this assumption does not hold in practice because both $\mathbf{w}_*$ and A_1 are unknown. Nevertheless, the criterion is still valid, as illustrated by the computer simulations in section 6. The explanation is twofold. On the one hand, when some recursive algorithm is used to compute $\hat{\mathbf{w}}$ and $\hat{A}_1$ (see next section), the p.d.f. of the soft symbol estimates $y(n)$ gets closer and closer to the *a priori* assumed one as the successively obtained parameter estimates converge to the desired values $\mathbf{w}_*$ and A_1 . On the other hand, criterion (12) is equivalent to a partial minimization of the Kullback-Leibler Distance (KLD) between the actual p.d.f. of $y(n)$, $f_y(\cdot)$, and the target p.d.f. [6].

4 ITERATIVE IMPLEMENTATION

Unfortunately, it is not possible to find a closed form solution to problem (12) and, therefore, some recursive optimization algorithm must be used to obtain the parameter estimates $[\hat{\mathbf{w}}, \hat{A}_1]$. We will first convert problem (12) into an unconstrained form using the Generalized Sidelobe Canceller (GSC) decomposition [7],

$$\mathbf{w}_* = \mathbf{w}_q - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{w}_u \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_q$ is the quiescent vector chosen to ensure that the constraint is verified, the $L \times (L - P)$ blocking matrix $\mathbf{B}$ spans the left null subspace of $\mathbf{C}_1(0)$ and $\mathbf{w}_u$ is the $(L - P) \times 1$ unconstrained part of $\mathbf{w}_*$. Both $\mathbf{w}_q$ and $\mathbf{B}$ are completely determined by the constraint, so they are fixed. Then, problem (12) turns into

$$\hat{\Theta} = \arg \max_{\Theta} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(\Theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} \log E_b \left[e^{-\frac{|y(n) - A_1 b|^2}{\sigma_f^2}} \right] \right\} \quad (14)$$

where $\Theta = [\mathbf{w}_u, A_1]$.

In this work, we propose to compute Θ using the EM algorithm [8] that provides an iterative procedure to perform ML estimation when direct maximization of the likelihood is not feasible. The Expectation Maximization (EM) approach assumes the existence of some unobserved data that, if known, would simplify the estimation problem. The observations alone are referred to as the incomplete data set, whereas the complete data set is the union of the observations and the unobserved data. Parameter estimation is iteratively carried out in two steps. The expectation (E) step consists of computing sufficient statistics of the complete data using the observations and the current parameter estimates. The subsequent maximization (M) step consists of re-estimating the parameters using the complete data sufficient statistics. In our problem, the incomplete data are the soft estimates $\mathbf{y}$ and the complete data set is given by the extended vectors $\mathbf{y}_e(n) = [y(n) \ b_1(n)]^T$, $n = 0, \dots, K - 1$. The E and M steps are comprised

into the single iterative rule

$$\hat{\Theta}_{i+1, i+1} = \arg \min_{\Theta} \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{\mathbf{y}_e(n) | y(n); \hat{\Theta}_{i, i}} \left[|y(n) - A_1 b_1(n)|^2 \right] \right\} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_e(n) | y(n)$ denotes conditioning of the complete data to the observed data and $\hat{\Theta}$ and $\hat{\Theta}_{i, j}$ denote $[\hat{\mathbf{w}}_u, \hat{A}_1]$ and $[\hat{\mathbf{w}}_u(i), \hat{A}_1(j)]$, respectively.

Since the solution of (15) w.r.t. to the parameter vector Θ is rather involved, we propose to use the SAGE algorithm [8] which is a suitable modification of the EM approach that gives separate updating rules for different parameter subsets. In our case, $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_u$ and $\hat{A}_1$ can be estimated as

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_u(i+1) = \left(\mathbf{B}^H \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} \mathbf{x}(n) \mathbf{x}^H(n) \mathbf{B} \right)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{B}^H \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} \mathbf{x}(n) \mathbf{x}^H(n) \mathbf{w}_q - \mathbf{B}^H \hat{A}_1^*(i) \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{b|y(n); \hat{\Theta}_{i, i}} [b^*] \mathbf{x}(n) \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{A}_1(i+1) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{b|y(n); \hat{\Theta}_{i, i}} [|b|^2] \right)^{-1} \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{b|y(n); \hat{\Theta}_{i+1, i}} [b^*] y(n) \quad (17)$$

where we have also used the fact that the only random part in $\mathbf{y}_e(n) | y(n)$ is $b_1(n)$ and we have calculated the conditioned expectations using the Bayes theorem.

5 ADAPTIVE IMPLEMENTATION

In order to reduce the computational load of the iterative EM algorithm (16)-(17), we propose an alternative adaptive implementation based on the Recursive Least Squares (RLS) algorithm. Let us rewrite (16) as

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_u(i+1) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{K-1} \mathbf{x}_b(n) \mathbf{x}_b^H(n) \right)^{-1} \times \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} \mathbf{x}_b(n) \left(b_q^*(n) - E_{b|y(n); \hat{\Theta}_i} [\hat{A}_1^*(i) b^*] \right) \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_b(n) = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{x}(n)$ and $b_q^*(n) = \mathbf{x}^H(n) \mathbf{w}_q$. Applying the *matrix inversion lemma* in (18) and defining

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}(0) &= \mathbf{I}_{L-P} \\ \mathbf{P}(i) &= \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{x}_b}^{-1} = \mathbf{P}(i-1) - \mathbf{k}(i) \mathbf{x}_b^H(i) \mathbf{P}(i-1) \quad i > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

and

$$\mathbf{k}(i) = \frac{\mathbf{P}(i-1) \mathbf{x}_b(i)}{1 + \mathbf{x}_b^H(i) \mathbf{P}(i-1) \mathbf{x}_b(i)} \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_{L-P}$ is the $(L - P) \times (L - P)$ identity matrix and $\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{x}_b} = \sum_{i=0}^{K-1} \mathbf{x}_b(i) \mathbf{x}_b^H(i)$, we get the desired adaptive rule for updating the filter coefficients,

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}(i) = \hat{\mathbf{w}}(i-1) + \mathbf{k}(i) [d(i) - \mathbf{x}_b^H(i) \mathbf{w}(i-1)] \quad (21)$$

Figure 2: MSE vs SNR. *Left:* $K = 300$ observation vectors. *Right:* $K = 600$ observation vectors.

where $d(i) = b_q^*(i) - E_{b|y(i), \hat{\Theta}_i}[\hat{A}_1^*(i)b^*]$.

6 COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

Finally, we present computer simulations that illustrate the validity of our approach. We have considered an asynchronous DS CDMA communication system with $N = 7$ users transmitting QPSK symbols, length $L = 16$ random binary spreading sequences and length $P = 4$ unknown dispersive channels.

Figure 2 (left) plots the Mean Square Error (MSE) attained with the proposed algorithms for several values of the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), defined as $SNR = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\mathbf{d}_1^H(0)\mathbf{d}_1(0)E|b_1|^2}{\sigma_q^2}$, when the number of observation vectors available to estimate the receiver coefficients is $K = 300$. It is apparent that the proposed iterative EM receiver performs practically the same as the theoretical LCMV receiver constructed using the same linear constraint as in the proposed receivers and perfect knowledge of the multiuser channel matrix. As expected, the adaptive EM receiver performs close to the theoretical limit but its convergence is worse than the iterative one. In this figure we have also plotted the MSE achieved by the practical LCMV receiver constructed using the RLS algorithm. It can be seen that the performance of the practical LCMV receiver is considerably worse than the theoretical one.

We have repeated the previous experiment for $K = 600$ observation vectors and plotted the resulting curve in figure 2 (right). It is apparent that the adaptive EM algorithm performance matches the theoretical limit and the practical LCMV receiver also approaches this limit. Nevertheless, its convergence is still poorer for the medium to high SNR region.

7 CONCLUSIONS

We have introduced a new blind approach to MAI and ISI rejection for DS CDMA systems based on the ML principle. The method is blind because it does not require the transmission of training sequences. Instead, it exploits the knowledge of the transmitted symbols p.d.f. Two

possible implementations are suggested: an iterative one based on the SAGE algorithm and an adaptive one that uses the matrix inversion lemma in order to reduce the computational complexity.

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